

GALL STONE DISEASE - CAUSES, SYMPTOMS, TYPES, DIAGNOSIS, TREATMENT, PREVENTION

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Abstract: *Gallstone disease (as well as gallstones, gallstone disease), cholelithiasis (Greek cholḗ - grass, bile, lithos - stone) - this is gallbladder (cholecystolithiasis) and gallstones. The disease is characterized by the formation of stones (concretions) in the airways (choledocholithiasis). Stones are formed as a result of bile pigments, cholesterol, certain types of proteins, calcium salts, bile infection, its stagnation (drip, stasis), and impaired lipid metabolism.*

The disease can be accompanied by pain in the right lower rib, colic, jaundice. Because medical practice has shown that other treatments for gallstones are ineffective, surgical intervention is required. The disease can be complicated by cholecystitis, fistula formation, peritonitis.

GALL STONE DISEASE

Gallstone disease is a disease characterized by impaired synthesis and circulation of bile in the hepatobiliary system, which leads to the formation of stones in the gallbladder and bile ducts as a result of impaired cholesterol or bilirubin metabolism. Gallstone disease is considered dangerous because it can lead to serious complications with a high risk of death.

Risk factors for developing gallstones include:

Old and young;

Taking drugs that affect cholesterol and bilirubin metabolism (fibrates, menopausal estrogens, ceftriaxone, octreotide);

Genetic factors (maternal gallstone disease);

Eating disorders (obesity, rapid weight loss, starvation, increased levels of cholesterol and high-density lipoproteins, hypertriglyceridemia);

Multiple pregnancies;

Metabolic diseases (diabetes, fermentopathies, metabolic syndrome);

Diseases of the gastrointestinal tract (Crohn's disease, duodenal and bile duct diverticula, biliary tract infection);

Postoperative conditions (after gastric resection, oral vagoectomy).

Gallstones are more common in women.

CAUSES OF STONE FORMATION

When the quantitative ratio of bile components is disturbed, solid formations occur in the body, which over time grow and coalesce, resulting in the formation of stones. Cholelithiasis is most often associated with impaired cholesterol metabolism (excess bile). Cholesterol-rich bile is called lithogeny.

Excess cholesterol is caused by:

Obesity and high cholesterol intake;

Decreased bile acid secretion (decreased estrogen secretion, gallbladder deposition, functional insufficiency of hepatocytes);

Decreased levels of phospholipids, such as bile acids, that prevent cholesterol and bilirubin from solidifying and settling;

Constipation in the biliary system (thickening of the bile due to the absorption of water and bile acids in the gallbladder).

TREATMENT OF GALL STONE DISEASE

In uncomplicated forms of gallstones, the detection of stones in the gallbladder, as a rule, does not require specific treatment, mainly following the tactics of waiting. If acute or chronic calculous cholecystitis develops, gallbladder removal is indicated as the source of stone formation. Surgical intervention (cholecystectomy) is performed by laparoscopic or incision of the abdominal cavity, depending on the condition of the body, pathological changes in the walls of the bladder and surrounding tissues, the size of the concretions. When technically necessary, a small-perforated cholecystectomy can always be performed with an abdominal incision.

There are ways to dissolve the concretions with ursodeoxychol and xenoxycholic acid preparations, but this type of therapy does not lead to a cure for gallstones and new stones can form over time. Another method of stone removal is pulse-wave lithotripsy, which is used in patients who have only one concretion and do not suffer from acute inflammation of the gallbladder or ducts.

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